

SITUATIONS AND NEEDS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE ELDERLY IN BANG RIN COMMUNITY, MUANG DISTRICT, RANONG PROVINCE

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to understand the Situations and needs in the management of the elderly in Bang Rin Community, Muang District, Ranong Province. Indeed, elderly people are facing different kinds of problems all over the world due to different factors. However, the stratified sampling method was used to collect the data for this study to ensure that the respondents should provide accurate information on the Likert scale five-point questionnaire. The considered sample size for this study was 450. However, the study demonstrates that there is a critical role of health facilities, financial support, and housing in the management and care of the elderly people in Bang Rin community, Muang District, Ranong Province. This study provides significant implications for both theoretical and practical implementations for the government and other stakeholders to consider these implementations for getting better results and improving the lives of elderly people.

Keywords. Elderly People, Elderly Management, Elderly Care, Elderly Services, and Elderly Health

1. Introduction

In the current developing era, it has become critical for the government to protect and manage the facilities for the elderly people of the society. It is due to the reason that not only in the developing but at the same time, in the developed countries elderly people are facing a different kind of crisis in their living standard and management (Lucantoni, Principi, Socci, Zannella, & Barbabella, 2022). No doubt, there is a different kind of factors that are contributing to the crisis of elderly people in both developing and developed countries. In this regard, the government should be responsible to ensure that the elderly people of the country are provided with equal opportunities and they are getting all the things according to their basic human rights. Moreover, the elderly people who are not provided with equal opportunities, these people must be protected by society and the government at the same time.

Health facilities refer to the basic health facilities provided to the people of any society for their sustainable life (Puntub & Greiving, 2022). However, not only the young but at the same time, the elderly people of the society are also required better health facilities because they are a part of the society, and they must be protected equally. Financial support refers to the financial help of any individual in monetary terms to make him capable of fulfilling his needs (Sobhani et al., 2022). However, in the societies in which people are provided with financial support, these societies are growing rapidly because the system of financially supporting each other leads the society into a progressive way (Demeusy, Handley, Manly, Sturm, & Toth, 2021). Housing refers to the provision of opportunities to the people for improving their living standards and protecting them with shelter. In this regard, in developed countries housing facilities are provided to every individual while considering it as a basic human right. However, on the other

hand in backward countries, housing facilities are not provided to elderly people. Elderly care refers to the management of systematic strategies to protect adult people socially and psychologically (Charoenwat et al., 2022). According to Brooks et al. (2022), it is important to understand that if a society is collectively failed to protect elderly people, then in result not only in the short term but in the long term the society would face problems.

The objective of this study is to determine to what extent the management of elderly life is being done. This study is understanding the critical role of health, financial support, and housing in the management of the living standards of elderly people. In this regard, the study is designed based on a study framework that is developed to understand, the relationship between housing health facilities and financial support is influencing and contributing to the management of elderly people (Numpong et al., 2022). Importantly, this study would provide the appropriate solutions based on the conclusion to understand how elderly people can improve their living standards with the support of government and the society.

This study is a significant contribution to the literature because no earlier study has discussed the role of health facilities, financial support, and housing to identify their relationship with the management of elderly people's life. In this way, this study provides a theoretical implementation that would be useful for the government and other policy-making entities to ensure that the critical factor discussed in this study should be considered while making policy for elderly people (Jaya & Wulandari, 2022). Similarly, this study also has practical implementation because it was observed that in practice the government and the society are not focusing on the critical factor to protect and manage the life of the elderly people. In this regard, this study provides significant implementation while addressing the gap in the literature as well as in practice to manage the life of elderly people to the advanced level.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Role of Health Facilities in Elderly Care

The elderly people of any community are suffering once because they are not provided with the appropriate facilities to spend their meaningful life in the best way (Ferschmann, Bos, Herting, Mills, & Tamnes, 2022). In this regard, according to Miftachurochmah and Sukanti (2022), different countries and governments are implementing different kinds of strategies to improve the lives of elderly people in society. However, it is understood that the different cultural variants are present in the society, then it has become critical to protect the elderly people in the society with dignity and prosperity (de Figueiredo et al., 2021). In this regard, it is important to understand that there is a critical role of health facilities for elderly people because they are needed with it. On the one hand, some countries are providing opportunities for the elderly people to improve their health standards by taking free hospitals and medicines by the government (Chang, Tsou, Chen, & Hung, 2022). The people of these countries are getting success based on their parameters because they believe that their success is not limited to their wisdom but would contribute to society when they are provided with better health opportunities. According to Sun et al. (2022), there are countries where the elderly people are facing a different kind of crisis in getting the help facility because the government is not

providing theory at facilities according to the advanced level. In this way, it is noted that the elderly people of the community are not getting the right opportunity for the best facilitation of their health and other activities. In developing countries, hospitality services are provided to the elderly people at the priority level because it is under to that if they are not provided with the proper hospital and health facilities, as result they would be disturbed to a greater extent (McGorry et al., 2022). However, in the developed countries the government is making strategies to improve the policy statement and ensure that the elderly people are provided with the best opportunities as they are provided in the developed countries. Moreover, not only the government sector but at the same time the private sector is concerned to provide the health opportunity to the elderly people because their health is critical to society. Importantly, if the elderly people are not provided with the right of facilities, as result there would be the collapse of ideology and they would be in danger for the remaining life. The doctors and the society at the same time should contribute to providing the right facilities to the right elderly people at the right time to protect their health wealth and mental capabilities. In Denmark and Norway, the governments are making strategies and implementing the strategy to provide better health facilities to the elderly people for the prosperity of society (Khaonuan, 2022).

H1. There is a relationship between health facilities and elderly care.

2.2 Role of Financial Support in Elderly Health

For elderly people, financial support is critical because they are at risk of social and most of them are not supported by their families to fulfill their basic needs. In this regard, it is critical to determine that to what extent the elderly people are provided with the help and financial facilities by the society and the government at the same time to ensure that they are fulfilling their needs according to their requirements (Astiarani, Putri, Fitriah, & Kurniawan, 2022). In this way, it is not only the responsibility of the family but at the same time it is the responsibility of the concerned government that the advanced level strategies should be designed and policy statement should be modified according to the requirement of the elderly people, and they must be provided with the final financial support (AlMarzooqi et al., 2022). In the countries in which the elderly people are provided with financial support, these countries are getting prosperity, and the level of diseases in the elderly people in these countries is low because they are getting all the opportunities and their requirements are being fulfilled. However, on the other hand, the country that is badly failed to provide a different kind of facilities to the people of the society, in these countries people are not provided with equal opportunities, but they are left blind and the government is not considered to ensure their financial support (Moallef et al., 2022). As a result of less attention paid to the elderly people and no fun and food, these elderly people are facing a different kind of disease and other related issues because they are not supported by society and the government at the same time. Denmark and Norway work to ensure that the people are provided with equal opportunities and they are respected by society as they were respected when they were young. Moreover, with financial support, elderly people survive in society and live prosperous life. In backward countries, the elderly people are facing a crisis in terms of medicine and food because they are not provided with equal opportunities and other government policies to get support from the government in the terms of the elderly fund or the

financial fund (Li, Chang, Wang, & Zhou, 2022). Likewise, it is also noted that the elderly people of backward countries are dying early because of their bad health conditions and less attention paid to their facilities. However, the focus of elderly people is not limited but if they would be provided with financial support, they would develop their best strategies to live and according to their life. According to the United Nations Human Right Commission, elderly people should be protected by the government of every country to ensure that they are provided with the call opportunities and they are not considered as the left behind people in the society (Estrada, Priego, Morente, & Mora, 2022).

H2. There is a relationship between financial support and elderly care.

2.3 Role of Housing in Elderly Health

In modern times, it has become critical for elderly people that they must be provided with the opportunity of housing to live their remaining life. In this regard, it is important to understand that the elderly people that are provided with better housing opportunities, are living their life effectively and are considered respected members of society (Puntub & Greiving, 2022). It is due to the reason that better housing is the requirement of every individual human being and if the human beings are provided with the right opportunities at the right time. On the other hand, according to Demeusy et al. (2021), the elderly people that are not provided with an equal opportunity, and they are left behind in the terms of housing and are forced to live with the other people on the road, resulting in the elderly people are not respected by society and provided opportunities to get the things done appropriately. However, the elderly people must understand their responsibilities and they must aware of their human right to housing because until and unless they are not aware of their human right of housing the society would not cooperate with them, and they would not be provided with equal opportunity in the term of housing and other activities (Jaya & Wulandari, 2022). In this regard, it is critical to understand that the developing countries should provide housing opportunities to the elderly people on the concept of developed countries, where the elderly people are entertaining their lives in the best and most effective way with all kinds of necessary facilities. No doubt, housing is the critical success factor in the life of individuals, but over time when the elderly people are growing the need for housing is important to them where they are provided with the opportunities of nursing and other activities, where they could easily remain their remaining life. In this way, the government of the developing countries should focus on the opportunities and develop strategies to implement and build housing facilities for the elderly people, and they must be provided with equal opportunities in the location of houses (Rahmah, 2022). Also, with the concept of this not only the living need of elderly people would be entertained, but at the same time they must be protected with housing and they should not be provided with any kind of opportunities for stress and anxiety. Indeed, the elderly people that are living in better housing and are provided with better nursing opportunities is their life is greater heaven than the elderly people of the other regions.

H3. There is a relationship between housing and elderly care.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Questionnaire and Data Collection

To proceed with this study, the questionnaire was prepared on the 5-point Likert scale to collect the data from the respondents. However, the questionnaire was divided into two different sections to proceed with the study. On the one hand, in the first section, the questionnaire was designed to get the data related to the demographic information of the respondents. However, on the other hand, the questionnaire was designed to have scale items related to each variable. Moreover, the scale items for each variable were carefully taken from the earlier studies to ensure that nothing is different from the study. However, the stratified sampling method was adopted to collect data from the respondents and the target sample was 450. In this regard, a brief introduction about the study was provided to the respondents to make them aware of the purpose of the study. After providing the information related to the purpose of the study, the respondents were asked to fulfill the questionnaire according to their information. In last, after getting the response of the respondents on the questionnaire the questionnaire was collected back and the Smart PLS 3 software was considered for data analysis.

4. Findings

4.1 Convergent Validity

In this study, the Smart PLS 3 software was used to analyze the data to check the convergent validity (see Figure 1). In this regard, the factor loadings, Cronbach Alpha, CR, and AVE values were taken to understand the reliability and validity. According to the results, the values of factor loadings for each variable were greater than 0.60 which is recommended by Wong (2013) for modern studies. However, in the same way, the values of CR were greater than 0.70 which is recommended by Wong (2013) for modern studies. Importantly, all the values of AVE were greater than 0.50, which is also recommended for modern studies (see Table 1). In this regard, it is observed that there is a clear validity and reliability in the scale items taken for this study.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 1: Factor Loadings, Alpha, CR and AVE

Variables	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Elderly Care	EC1	0.955	0.950	0.968	0.909
	EC2	0.968			
	EC3	0.937			
Financial Support	FS1	0.641	0.792	0.850	0.535
	FS2	0.736			
	FS3	0.855			
	FS4	0.744			
	FS5	0.661			
Health Facilities	HF1	0.735	0.732	0.820	0.579
	HF2	0.682			
	HF3	0.772			
	HF4	0.645			
	HF5	0.614			
Housing	HG1	0.930	0.901	0.933	0.777
	HG2	0.933			
	HG3	0.916			
	HG4	0.730			

4.2 Discriminant Validity

In this study, the discrimination validity was also tested to ensure that there is a clear distinction between the variables and the scale items taken for each variable. In this way, the HTMT method was used to check the discriminant validity with the help of the Smart PLS 3 calculations. In this regard, all the values for each variable were not greater than 0.90 which is recommended by Wong (2013) for future studies. In this regard, there is a clear discriminant validity between the variables taken for each scale item (see Table 2).

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

	Elderly Care	Financial Support	Health Facilities	Housing
Elderly Care				
Financial Support	0.658			
Health Facilities	0.730	0.832		
Housing	0.666	0.684	0.815	

4.3 The PLS-SEMs Results

This section of the study is based on the direct effect available in Figure 3. To begin with, H1 was tested to check its significance and according to the results Health Facilities has a significant effect on Elderly Care ($\beta = 0.226$, $T = 3.086$, $P = 0.002$) and H1 is supported. H2 was tested to check its significance and according to the results Financial Support has a significant effect on Elderly Care ($\beta = 0.297$, $T = 5.235$, $P = 0.000$) and H2 is supported. H3 was tested to check its significance and according to the results, Housing has a significant effect on Elderly Care ($\beta = 0.249$, $T = 3.586$, $P = 0.000$), and H3 is supported (see Table 3). Furthermore, t

Figure 3: Structural Model

Furthermore, the relationship between the health facilities and elderly care is presented in the histogram to get a proper understanding available in Figure 4. This relationship shows that there is a significant relationship between the health facility and elderly care.

Figure 4: Health Facilities and Elderly Care

Also, the relationship between financial support and elderly care is presented in the histogram available in Figure 5. Moreover, according to the figure, it is identified that there is a clear significant relationship between financial support and elderly care.

Figure 5: Financial Support and Elderly Care

Additionally, the relationship between housing and elderly care is also presented in the histogram available in figure 6. Based on the figure and identified results, it is clear that there is a significant relationship between housing and elderly people.

Figure 6: Housing and Elderly Care

Table 3: Direct Effects

Hypotheses	B	STDEV	T Values	P Values	Decision
H1. Health Facilities -> Elderly Care	0.226	0.073	3.086	0.002	Supported
H2. Financial Support -> Elderly Care	0.297	0.057	5.235	0.000	Supported
H3. Housing -> Elderly Care	0.249	0.069	3.586	0.000	Supported

5. Discussion and Conclusions

According to the results of H1, there is a significant relationship between health facilities and elderly care. It is a fact that healthcare facilities are critical for the development of integrated and sustainability in the life of the elder people, and the right direction for the greater benefit to the people of the society. However, some countries are not working on the battery health opportunities for the people, as a result, the expected life duration of the people is low because the mortality rate in these countries is high (Lucantoni et al., 2022). In this regard, the importance of healthcare facilities cannot be ignored and these parameters are critical to understanding while developing the Strategies for the better development of the community at the large level. On the other hand, the developed countries are collaborating with different entities to ensure that the people of the countries are provided with appropriate health facilities that are needed for success.

According to the results of H2, there is a significant relationship between financial support and elderly care. In this regard, it is important to understand that the people that are financially well and they are getting all the opportunities, these people are enjoying the best health facilities even in the elder age. On the one hand, according to Lucantoni et al. (2022), the people with strong financial backgrounds are getting the facility for better health. However, on the other hand, it is noted that the people that are not provided with equal opportunities to get the best health, as result these people are failed and they are not provided with equal opportunity to ensure that it is of their health.

According to the results of H3, there is a significant relationship between housing and elderly care. Indeed, the elderly care management authorities are considered that there is an important role of housing in protecting the life of elder people. It is because the elder people are needed

with housing. After all, it is also a basic human need. In this regard, the authorities are more concerned to ensure that the elder people are provided with opportunities equal to the appropriate strategies for getting better results in terms of health and other life-related issues. Indeed, the countries that are focusing more on the development of strategies for the elderly people, and improving the standard of living of elderly people to a greater extent for better development.

6. Theoretical and Practical Implications of the Study

This study has theoretical as well as practical implementation for better maintaining the health of elderly people. In this regard, the study addresses the theoretical gap in the literature that was not identified and discussed by any earlier study. This study demonstrates the relationship between health facilities, financial support, housing, and elderly care. The study emphasizes that without these factors, it would be completely difficult for the government and other stakeholders to provide better health and maintenance life facilities to the elderly people. In this way, the theoretical framework of the study is a greater contribution to the literature because it provides a detailed insight into the relationship of dependent and independent variables. Moreover, on the other hand, the study provides practical implications for the government and other policy-making people that they must be considered the role of the financial sport, health facilities, and housing to provide better facilities to the people. In a nutshell, this study highlights that without providing financial support and housing, it would not be appropriate and that's to facilitate the elderly people for their better future.

7. Limitations and Future Directions

This study has considered the critical factor of health facilities, financial support, and housing to understand the contribution of these factors in the elderly care and management system. However, there are not limited factors but the other factors that are also useful for the management of elderly care. In this regard, their study recommends that future studies should consider the critical role of old homage, government policies, and the old pension system for the management of elderly care. In this way, it would be the greatest contribution to the theory as well as in practice to show their elderly people are getting advantage and equal opportunities.

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